

Rapid and selective oxidation of alcohols to aldehydes and ketones with tetraethylammonium superoxide under microwave irradiation

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Manuscript received online 04 May 2012, revised 19 September 2012, accepted 29 September 2012

Abstract : An efficient method for the oxidation of alcohols to the corresponding aldehydes and ketones has been accomplished using *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide under microwave irradiation. The reaction is fast with good yields and straightforward workup.

Keywords : Alcohols, superoxide, microwave irradiation, oxidation.

Introduction

The selective oxidation of alcohols to aldehydes and ketones without forming over-oxidized product is one of the most fundamental and important processes in synthetic organic chemistry^{1,2} and various methods have been reported, for example, Dess-Martin oxidation³, Oppenauer oxidation⁴, Swern oxidation⁵, Collins reagent⁶, pyridinium chlorochromate⁷, pyridinium dichromate⁸ and Moffatt oxidation⁹. Moreover, several transition metals such as palladium¹⁰, ruthenium¹¹, molybdenum¹², manganese¹³, rhenium¹⁴, copper¹⁵, iron¹⁶, cobalt¹⁷, platinum¹⁸ and vanadium¹⁹ based aerobic and anaerobic systems have been developed for these transformations. However, the main drawbacks associated with these systems are troublesome workup, long reaction time, environmentally unfriendly metal waste and in majority of cases they require an elevated temperature for effective catalytic activity.

Superoxide ion (O_2^{\ominus}) is a reactive oxygen species (ROS) and is formed in all aerobic life forms by both enzymatic and non-enzymatic processes²⁰. From chemical view point, it is a multipotent reagent²¹⁻²³ and is achieved using chemical or electrochemical method^{24,25}. The use of microwave irradiation to simplify and improve classic organic reactions has become very popular technique because it often results in shorter reaction times, higher yields and cleaner reaction²⁶. Recent studies have shown that superoxide under microwave irradiation is an efficient reagent

for various organic transformations²⁷. In continuation to our research program on superoxide chemistry²⁸, we describe herein our result on the reactivity of *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide (Et_4NO_2) with different primary and secondary alcohols under microwave irradiation, affording corresponding aldehydes and ketones (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In the course of reaction, Et_4NO_2 was generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of KO_2 and Et_4NBr in dry DMF and was subsequently allowed to react with alcohols, under microwave irradiation. As an outcome, alcohols were readily oxidized to their corresponding aldehydes and ketones in good to excellent yields (Table 1).

The reaction was accomplished by using a 3.0 fold molar excess of KO_2 and 1.5 fold molar excess of Et_4NBr with respect to substrate. Each reaction was monitored by TLC for its completion. The products were fully identified by their physical and spectral data, which are in full agreement with the values described in literature²⁹

Table 1. Oxidation of alcohols by Et₄NO₂ under microwave irradiation

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time MW (min)	Yield (%)
1	PhCH ₂ OH	PhCHO	1.5	75
2	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -PhCH ₂ OH	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -PhCHO	1.5	85
3	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -PhCH ₂ OH	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -PhCHO	1.5	84
4	<i>p</i> -MeO-PhCH ₂ OH	<i>p</i> -MeO-PhCHO	1.5	74
5	<i>p</i> -Cl-PhCH ₂ OH	<i>p</i> -Cl-PhCHO	1.5	71
6	PhCH(OH)CH ₃	PhCOCH ₃	2.0	75
7	PhCH(OH)Ph	PhCOPh	2.0	87
8	<i>p</i> -Cl-PhCH(OH)Ph	<i>p</i> -Cl-PhCOPh	2.0	84
9	PhCOCH(OH)Ph	PhCOCOPh	2.5	65
10	Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	2.0	80
11	2-Cyclohexenol	2-Cyclohexenone	2.5	62

It is important to mention that tetraethylammonium superoxide alone in the absence of microwave was able to achieve benzoic acid³⁰ in considerably longer reaction time (9 h) with benzyl alcohol. To observe the sole role of microwave on the above reactions, some blank experiments under microwave irradiation in absence of tetraethylammonium superoxide were also carried out resulting in no net reactions. However when microwave is coupled with superoxide, the rate of reaction is dramatically enhanced and without forming over-oxidized product, thereby highlighting the significance of microwave-superoxide combination.

In order to optimize the yield of product from substrate, the effect of molar concentration of KO₂ and Et₄NBr was studied in detail with particular reference to benzyl alcohol. The results of investigation are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of molar ratios on the yield of product (benzaldehyde)

Entry	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ OH	KO ₂	Et ₄ NBr	Product yield (%)
1	1.0	1.0	Nil	10
2	1.0	1.0	1.0	32
3	1.0	2.0	2.0	56
4	1.0	2.0	1.0	55
5	1.0	3.0	1.5	75
6	1.0	4.0	2.0	76
7	1.0	5.0	2.5	76

With a view to investigate the effect of solvents on the product yield, the reaction of benzyl alcohol with KO₂ and Et₄NBr (1 : 3 : 1.5 molar ratio) was carried out in a number of solvents like DMF, DMSO and CH₃CN (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the yield of product (benzaldehyde)

Solvent	Yield (%)
DMSO	58
DMF	75
CH ₃ CN	Intractable products

Based on product isolation and existing chemistry^{21-23,30,31} of \bar{O}_2 , a plausible mechanism is outlined for the above transformation (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

Potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide were procured from E. Merck, and were used as received. Dry DMF of Aldrich, was stored over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to use. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were run on a JEOL AL300 FT-NMR and the chemical shift are expressed as δ (ppm), using TMS as internal reference. A Kenstar digital microwave oven at full power (800 W) was used.

General procedure for the reaction of in situ generated tetraethylammonium superoxide with alcohols under microwave irradiation: A mixture of potassium superox-

ide (0.43 g; 0.006 mol) and tetraethylammonium bromide (0.63 g; 0.003 mol) were weighted under nitrogen atmosphere using an atmosbag and were transferred into the two-necked round bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer, nitrogen inlet and a Liebig condenser protected by calcium chloride drying tube. Dry dimethylformamide (15 ml) was added to it and the mixture was agitated magnetically for 15 min to facilitate the formation of tetraethylammonium superoxide. The alcohol (0.002 mol) was finally introduced and the contents of vessel were subjected to microwave irradiation for the specified time (Table 1). The reaction-mixture was poured into a beaker containing brine solution (15 ml) and cold water (15 ml) and then extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 20 ml). The combined organic extract was dried over Na₂SO₄ (anhyd.), filtered and evaporated to yield pure product.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have developed an efficient method for the selective and rapid oxidation of alcohols to the corresponding aldehydes and ketones under non-aqueous aprotic conditions and microwave irradiation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to UGC, New Delhi for financial support.

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